

Irregular semi-empirical dipole-moment function for carbon monoxide and line lists for all its isotopologues verified for extremely high overtone transitions†

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In our recent publication [JQSRT, 2021, 272, 107803] (Medvedev21), we discussed the problem of which restrictions must be imposed onto the diatomic functions in order that they would be capable of predicting, at least in part, the intensities of yet unobserved lines. The most general requirement to fulfil is that they must obey all known theoretical restrictions. Recently, the first steps in this direction were made by constructing, for carbon monoxide, a semi-empirical fully analytical mass-corrected potential-energy function (PEF) [Meshkov *et al.* JQSRT, 2018, 217, 262] and a mass-independent dipole-moment function (DMF), Medvedev21 and [Meshkov *et al.*, JQSRT, 2022, 280, 108090], with correct behavior in the limits of small and large inter-atomic separations. Both the PEF and DMF were fitted not only to the experimental line positions and transition moments but also to their *ab initio* values. A few additional requirements to the DMF were formulated, including the straight NIDL of [Medvedev, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2012, 137, 174307] and stability of predictions with respect to variations of the model DMF parameters caused by variations of the database to which the model was fitted. In this paper, the irregular DMF with branch points proposed in Medvedev21 is modified by increasing the rate of reaching the long-range limit and also by decreasing the number of adjustable parameters. In order to ensure the reliability of the predictions, a few regular model DMFs with no singularities in any finite part of the complex plane and a rational DMF are considered for the purpose of comparison. The idea behind such an approach is that similar intensity predictions of the DMFs with cardinally different analytical properties will testify the validity of the results obtained and will provide for a rough estimate of the prediction errors. The line lists for all CO isotopologues are generated in the range of quantum numbers $v' = 1-41$, $\Delta v \leq 15$, $J \leq 100$ ($J \leq 200$ for 0-0 and 1-0 bands). The validity of the calculated intensities up to $\Delta v = 15$ is demonstrated. Estimates of the expected errors of the calculated line intensities in the 7-0 band are given.

1 Introduction

There is no need to tell about the importance of CO in the terrestrial, solar, and exoplanet atmospheres and in the interstellar medium, see e.g. Meshkov *et al.*¹ (Meshkov22). In 2015, Li *et al.*² (Li15) developed a fully empirical dipole moment function (DMF) in the form of a sixth-order polynomial based on the available experimental data. The *ab initio* DMF values were also calculated in the range of bond length $r = 1.5-4$ a.u., and a semi-empirical piece-wise DMF was constructed. The latter was given by the empirical DMF in the range between the turning points of the $v = 6$ state ($0.99-1.34 \text{ \AA}$)³ and the spline-interpolated *ab initio* points outside. Using the empirical potential energy function (PEF) due to Coxon and Hajigeorgiou⁴ (Coxon04), Li *et al.* calculated the line lists that have been used in the modern spectroscopic databases HITRAN⁵ and others. However, the extrapolation ability of the DMF beyond the observed transitions was not investigated.

The traditional task of the theoretical molecular spectroscopy is to replace the actual experimental transition intensities with the line lists calculated with use of the model PEFs and DMFs. Paper Meshkov22 is devoted to performing this task for CO by updating the line lists up to the fifth overtone inclusive. The second task, which has not been previously given any attention to the best of our knowledge, is to create such models that would be capable of predicting, at least in part, yet unobserved lines. In order to perform this task and to reach “completeness in both vibrational and rotational states”^{6,7}, *the models must obey all known theoretical restrictions*. Recently, a semi-empirical mass-corrected PEF of CO with physical behavior in the limits of small and large inter-atomic separations has been constructed⁸ (Meshkov18). The model was fitted not only to the experimental data but also to the *ab initio* data. In paper⁹ (Medvedev21), we extended such an approach to construct a semi-empirical DMF with correct behavior in the asymptotic limits and fitted to both the experimental transition dipole moments and the *ab initio* DMF values. In this paper, we continue moving in this direction by investigating the analytical properties of the molecular functions necessary for successful predictions. We develop an improved irregular DMF, calculate the line lists with use of the Meshkov18 PEF, and show that it provides for reliable predictions of the intensities up to the highest overtone transitions included in the present line lists.

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2 Preliminary remarks

We start with the notion that our knowledge, both experimental and *ab initio*, about the intrinsic molecular DMF is restricted by point-wise data whereas, in order to calculate the line intensities, we need a function that provides for the DMF values at any r . If we are interested only in the low- $\Delta\nu$ transitions, any function can be used, e.g. piece-wise DMF (Li15) or piece-wise polynomial interpolation of PEF and DMF,¹⁰ as well as Padé approximants.^{11–13} However, when it goes about high overtones, the situation is different. Thus, we have $N \approx 1000$ experimental data points for CO transitions with $\Delta\nu \leq 6$, and we can invent many model DMFs that fit these data with a good dimensionless deviation, $DD \equiv \sqrt{\chi^2/N} \approx 1$. Yet, predictions for the 7-0 band can vary enormously (Medvedev21). It follows that some restrictions must be imposed onto the model DMF.

Some necessary restrictions have been formulated already: the function must 1) be analytical¹⁴; 2) obey the theoretically established short- and long-range behavior^{15–17}; in particular, they must be fitted simultaneously to the experimental transition dipole moments (TDMs) and *ab initio* DMF points; 3) possess branch points in the complex plane⁹; 4) be insensitive to variations in the database⁹; and 5) provide for the straight NIDL^{9,18–20}. The latter condition is a bit difficult to understand, therefore a numerical illustration is in order to supplement the theoretical derivation in Medvedev’s papers.^{18,21}

Fig. 1 The $\nu \leftarrow 0$ TDM values of the R0 line for power DMFs (black pluses, red circles, and blue rhombs are for $d(r) = 1, x, x^2$, respectively) normalized to their values for $\nu = 3$ (left ordinate) and the ratios of the TDMs ($d(r) = x$, green triangles, and x^2 , magenta squares) to the overlap integral ($d(r) = 1$, right ordinate). Color online.

Let us calculate the $\nu \leftarrow 0$ TDMs for the R0 line with Meshkov22 PEF and three simplest power functions, $d(r) = 1, x$, and x^2 , where $x = (r - r_e)/r_e$. In Fig. 1, the $\nu=0$ TDM normalised to the 3-0 TDM are plotted in the NIDL coordinates, i.e. logarithm of the TDM (or intensity) vs square root of the upper-state energy, E' , over the harmonic frequency, ω . We see that the plots are straight lines and they all have identical slopes. This means that all three sets of TDMs contain a common factor that governs the exponential decay of the TDM with the overtone num-

ber. Then it stands to reason that the straight NIDL line with a given slope is a property of the molecular potential. Especially prominent is the TDM for $d(r) = 1$ because it is merely the overlap integral of the wave functions, i.e. it depends solely on the potential. It was established theoretically^{18,22} and confirmed by direct numerical investigation²³ that the NIDL is associated with the repulsive branch of the potential, and that the NIDL slope is inversely proportional to the steepness of the repulsion.²⁴

The DMF affects only the common pre-factor, with an important exception. If we take a linear combination of the above DMFs, the TDM can turn to zero at some value of ν , which will give rise to an anomaly, i.e. a very low-intensity point dropped well below the NIDL line (not shown). Such anomalies are very common phenomenon in absorption,¹⁸ and recently they have been discovered in emission.²⁵

The role of the DMF is further clarified by plotting the ratio of the TDM for $d(r) = x, x^2$ to the overlap integral. Since the common factor responsible for the NIDL cancels, the ratio contains only the pre-factors and hence elucidates the contribution of the DMF. It is seen in Fig. 1 that it varies very slowly, within one order of magnitude, in the entire range of transitions where the individual TDMs vary by many orders of magnitude. Thus, the effect of DMF on the intensities is much smaller than that of PEF. However, the situation will change when the power increases: the NIDL will eventually break down because of too fast variation of the high-power DMF as compared to the wave function of the upper state (Medvedev21).

The rate of the intensity fall-off needs a special explanation, why is it so rapid? The common argument is that the high- ν wave functions are oscillating, which causes cancellation of the integrand resulting in the low integral values. However, the fall-off could be much slower, e.g. power-like, why is it exponential? **Owing to the NIDL, everybody of spectroscopists knows it is but hardly knows why.**

At this junction, we have to move into the complex plane of r because the NIDL was derived by considering the properties of the potential and dipole moment as functions of complex variable. Being physical molecular functions, they are determined at the real axis. However, any such function can be extended from the real axis into the complex plane in a unique fashion, and the path along which the transition integral is calculated can be shifted from the real axis into the complex plane²⁶. Far from the turning points, the wave functions are quasi-classical, i.e. they have the form of $\exp(i\hbar^{-1}S_\nu)$ (see Eq. (11) in Appendix A), where S_ν is classical action in a given state ν dependent only on the potential.²⁷ The actions are complex-valued along the path. In the case of overtone transitions, the path can be shifted in such a way that the value of the integrand is diminished to become on the order of the integral itself; in this case the transition integral is defined by the action difference for the initial and final states at the $r = 0$ end point,[‡] see Eq. (18) in Appendix A. This leads to the expo-

‡ In fact, imaginary S_ν can be calculated in the under-barrier region between the left turning point and some point $r_* \in [0-0.8] \text{ \AA}$ where the potential, $U(r)$, becomes much larger than the upper-state energy,¹⁸ E_ν , see Appendix A.

ponential fall-off of the intensity as manifested by the NIDL valid for high-enough overtones, typically for $\Delta\nu > 2$ (> 6 for CO, see Sec. 4.2). The derivation of the NIDL is presented in book¹⁹ Sec. 5.6.

The exponential intensity fall-off can be formally interpreted in terms of tunneling. As follows from Eqs. (18) and (21) in Appendix A, the probability of transition between states ν' and ν'' , i.e. the line intensity, can be written as product of three factors. The first one, $\exp(-2\hbar^{-1}|\text{Im}S_{\nu''}^*|)$, is the probability of tunneling from the left turning point in the lower state to the point r^* , see footnote[‡]. Since $U(r^*) \gg E_{\nu',\nu''}$, the system can cross to the higher state ν' with a probability on the order of unity, - this is the second factor. The third factor is $\exp(+2\hbar^{-1}|\text{Im}S_{\nu'}^*|)$, i.e. the probability of "back tunneling" from r^* to the left turning point in the upper state.

Returning to the properties of the physical functions, we can state that they are fully determined by the properties of their complex-valued counterparts. In particular, the main statement underlining the present approach reads that *the model functions extended into the complex plane must possess the same analytical properties as the respective intrinsic molecular functions*. In particular, they must have branch points corresponding to term intersections (**Medvedev21**), and they must decrease at infinity.

In this paper, we will numerically check the ability of the irregular, regular, and rational DMFs to provide for the straight NIDL, will present a new irregular DMF with improved properties as compared to **Medvedev21**, and calculate the line lists with this DMF. We will also check for stability of the calculated intensities with respect to a change in the database not considered in **Medvedev21**, namely when the function is fitted only to the *ab initio* data. Finally, we will compare the calculated intensities with the results obtained with various functions in order to ensure the reliability of the calculated line lists and in particular to estimate the uncertainties of the predictions for the 7-0 band.

3 Analytical forms of the DMF

In the course of this study, we found that the predictions for unobserved lines in the high-overtone bands of CO starting at $\Delta\nu = 4$ strongly depend on the DMF form (**Medvedev21**). Then, the question arises which form is closer to the true DMF. Obviously, many forms can be constructed, but only those can be trusted whose analytical properties most closely resemble those of the intrinsic DMF. Among such properties, we can name the presence of branch points due to term intersections in the complex plane (**Medvedev21**) and the DMF being decreasing at infinity. Various DMFs must also provide for the straight NIDL and for similar predictions of the unobserved lines. By the "similar", we mean the intensity values indistinguishable at the semi-logarithmic scale. Thus, it is important to have a few, at least two DMFs for comparison. Here and below, it goes without saying that all DMFs under consideration are fitted to one and the same database, provide for equally good descriptions of the database, and are subject to the same restrictions. In particular, all functions must satisfy the physically justified asymptotic behavior in both the united-atom and dissociation limits,¹⁵⁻¹⁷

$$d(r \rightarrow 0) \propto r^3; \quad d(r \rightarrow +\infty) = d_4 r^{-4}, \quad (1)$$

where

$$d_4 = -5.1 \pm 0.1 \text{ \AA} \quad (2)$$

was derived from the data of Ushakov *et al.*,¹⁷ see Supplementary material.[†]

One such function was proposed in **Medvedev21**. It has singularities, namely branch points in the complex plane of r due to term intersections, this is why we call it irregular in contrast to the regular functions having no singularities except for infinity.[§] Here, we advance a new version of the irregular DMF improved in two respects: 1) it reaches the long-range limit, Eq. (1), faster, which permits to obtain the correct value of the d_4 coefficient, Eq. (2); and 2) the number of the adjustable parameters is reduced from 16 to 13. The new irregular DMF has the form

$$d_{\text{irreg}}(r) = \frac{(1 - e^{-c_2 r})^3}{\sqrt{(r^2 - c_3^2)^2 + c_4^2} \sqrt{(r^2 - c_5^2)^2 + c_6^2}} \sum_{k=0}^6 b_k T_k(z_1(r)), \quad (3)$$

where $T_k(z)$ are the Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind, b_k are the corresponding expansion coefficients, and function

$$z_1(r) = 1 - 2e^{-c_1 r} \quad (4)$$

maps the $r \in [0, \infty]$ half-infinite interval to the $z \in [-1, +1]$ finite interval; b_0, \dots, b_6 and c_1, \dots, c_6 are linear and non-linear fitting parameters, respectively.

As explained in **Medvedev21**, the square roots in the denominator arose due to complex term crossings. Notably, they also describe the DMF maxima shown in Fig. 2. The mapping function of Eq. (4) reduces to the linear function, $z_1(r) \propto r$, in the main spectroscopic region ($\nu \leq 7$) of $r \in [0.99-1.36] \text{ \AA}$ (see Chackerian and Goorvitch³), so that the sum is just a 6th-order polynomial similar to the empirical one of **Li15**.

For comparison, several regular DMFs with no singularities in the complex plane except for infinity were invented by V.V. Meshkov in the course of our joint study **Meshkov22**. Here, one of them used in **Meshkov22** will be explored. The regular DMF depending on 2 non-linear and 11 linear, a total of 13 adjustable parameters, is

$$d_{\text{reg13}}(r) = (1 - e^{-c_1 r})^7 r^{-4} \sum_{k=0}^{10} b_k T_k(z_2(r)). \quad (5)$$

The mapping function in Eq. (5),

$$z_2(r) = 1 - 2e^{-c_2 r} \left(1 + c_2 r + \frac{1}{2} c_2^2 r^2 \right), \quad (6)$$

provides for the high density of the r grid in a vicinity of the equilibrium bond length, r_e , where the wavefunctions of the lowest vibrational levels studied are localized.

The function of Eq. (5) has a very transparent structure similar to the one employed by Wong *et al.*²⁸ for NO. The factor in front of the sum describes the limits of small and large r , Eq. (1), whereas the sum accounts for the middle-range behavior. Thus,

[§]If a function has no singularities at all, it is constant,²⁶ i.e. zero in the case of the DMF.

this function is the simplest one that is able to combine a good description of the available data (see Sec. 4.1) with the correct asymptotic behavior.

At first glance, this is the same function as that analyzed in **Medvedev21**. Remind that the latter gave a wavy NIDL and predicted a wrong 7-0 band. In the course of our group's study **Meshkov22**, this function was improved by imposing a very small weight, $w = 0.02$, in the least-squares fitting onto the *ab initio* points that permitted to decrease the number of parameters from 14 to 13 and thereby made the rotational distribution in the 7-0 band very similar to that obtained in **Medvedev21** with the irregular and polynomial functions. As we have already stated above, the coincidence of predictions on the semi-logarithmic scale made by several different DMFs testifies the validity of these predictions and provide for a rough estimate of the expected uncertainties of the calculations. However, in other respects this improved regular DMF cannot be also considered fully satisfactory, as we will see later.

As a second comparison function with analytical properties different from the above DMFs, we used the rational DMF of the form

$$d_{\text{rat14}}(r) = r^3 \frac{a_0(r-a_1)(r-a_2)(r-a_3)}{\prod_{i=1}^5 [(r-b_i)^2 + c_i^2]}. \quad (7)$$

It has 5 poles in the upper half-plane of complex r and 5 complex conjugate ones in the lower. The total number of variable parameters is 14.

Next, all three DMFs were fitted to the database derived in **Meshkov22**. It includes 505 TDM values calculated in **Meshkov22** from the experimental absorption intensities of the $\nu' \leftarrow \nu''$ ($\nu' = 0-6$, $\nu'' = 0,1$) bands of the main isotopologue plus 3 values of the permanent dipole moment from Refs. 29-31; six **Bul-dakov09**¹⁶ ACPF points at $r = 0.005-0.032 \text{ \AA}$; the ACPF points at $r = 0.5-17 \text{ \AA}$ and the CCSD(T) points at $r = 0.17-1.8 \text{ \AA}$ calculated in **Meshkov22**. Additionally, fitting of the DMF of Eq. (5) used the above-mentioned weight; fittings of the DMFs of Eqs. (3) and (7) also used the *ab initio* points of **Meshkov22** at $r = 0.1-0.5 \text{ \AA}$.

The fitted functions of Eqs. (3) and (7) are shown in Fig. 2 by the full and dashed lines, respectively (the DMF of Eq. (5) is not shown). Within the main spectroscopic region corresponding to $\nu \leq 7$ ($0.99-1.36 \text{ \AA}$)³, they all (including that not shown) coincide with each other with a high precision, about 10^{-5} D , i.e. 0.001%. This means that all the DMFs approach the intrinsic DMF within the spectroscopic region very closely, so that the difference of 0.01 D with the ACPF data seen in Fig. 3 is due to the ACPF error for sure. The FORTRAN codes of the irregular and rational DMFs are given in the Supplementary material.[†] The parameters of the fitted DMFs are shown in Table 1.

Figure 2 shows that all DMFs reproduce the *ab initio* points both in the asymptotic limits and in the middle part equally well except for the range of $r = 0.1-0.5 \text{ \AA}$, where the irregular function looks better than the rational DMF (and also better than the regular DMF not shown in the figure). More serious drawbacks of the regular functions will be demonstrated in the next section.

Fig. 2 The semi-empirical DMFs (full lines, irregular; dashed, rational) and the *ab initio* data (points with or without error bars) calculated by the CCSD(T) (pluses, $r = 0.17-1.8 \text{ \AA}$) and MR-ACPF (crosses, $r = 0.1-17 \text{ \AA}$) methods in **Meshkov22**. Squares, **Bul-dakov et al.**¹⁶

4 Comparison of the functions

Following **Medvedev21**, we will use, as reference, the 8th-order polynomial fitted to the experimental TDMs and to the ACPF points at $r = 0.5\text{-}2.1$ Å. We will compare the functions with respect to their ability to reproduce the input data, provide for the straight NIDLs and for the stability of the results in an aspect different from **Medvedev21** and to predict unobserved lines in the 7-0 band.

4.1 Data description

The quality of data description by the irregular function is seen in Table 2, where the relative line-intensity differences,

$$\delta I = |I_{\text{obs}} - I_{\text{calc}}| / I_{\text{calc}}, \quad (8)$$

averaged over the rotational distributions within the bands are shown. Obviously, the function is successful in reproducing the data included in the fit because the differences with the observed intensities are within a few percent for all bands and all of them are less than the experimental uncertainties. Similarly, the differences obtained with the regular (**Meshkov22**) and rational functions are also small and are nearly the same as for the irregular DMF (not shown).

Table 2 The relative differences (in %) between the calculated and measured absorption line intensities, Eq. (8), a total of 505 lines included in the fit, are compared with the experimental uncertainties. The differences are averaged over the rotational distributions within the bands.

band*1	No. of lines	irregular*2	exp
0-0	34	0.8	4.7
1-0	72	0.8	1.7
2-0	84	0.1	0.3
3-0	89	1.1	2.4
4-0	138	0.9	2.1
4-1	26	2.5	6.6
5-0	16	22	25
5-1	20	3.5	10
5-4 ³²	2	0.5	2.5
6-0	20	1.8	3.6
6-5 ³²	3	0.7	1.8
11-10 ³²	1	2	2.9

*1The sources of the data are cited in Sec. 5.

*2The same figures are valid for the regular and rational functions.

Fig. 3 Difference between the DMFs fitted to the full database and the ACPF data points with error bars. Black circles, irregular DMF; red squares, rational DMF; blue triangles, regular DMF. Color online.

Table 1 The fitted parameters of the DMFs defined by Eqs. (3) and (7).

Irregular	Rational
$c_1 = 0.76301 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$	$a_0 = -3.918 \text{ D\AA}^4$
$c_2 = 1.17729 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$	$a_1 = 0.39893177 \text{ \AA}$
$c_3 = 0.40267 \text{ \AA}$	$a_2 = 1.16695310 \text{ \AA}$
$c_4 = 0.01538 \text{ \AA}$	$a_3 = 3.97356997 \text{ \AA}$
$c_5 = 2.14020 \text{ \AA}$	$b_1 = 0.34083189 \text{ \AA}$
$c_6 = 2.27994 \text{ \AA}$	$c_1 = 0.09333640 \text{ \AA}$
$b_0 = 83.70049 \text{ D\AA}^4$	$b_2 = 2.29770919 \text{ \AA}$
$b_1 = -149.48440 \text{ D\AA}^4$	$c_2 = 0.78422052 \text{ \AA}$
$b_2 = 121.04143 \text{ D\AA}^4$	$b_3 = 1.15831442 \text{ \AA}$
$b_3 = -87.71820 \text{ D\AA}^4$	$c_3 = 1.47263177 \text{ \AA}$
$b_4 = 36.30155 \text{ D\AA}^4$	$b_4 = 0.74880496 \text{ \AA}$
$b_5 = -16.14795 \text{ D\AA}^4$	$c_4 = 0.96956301 \text{ \AA}$
$b_6 = 7.20707 \text{ D\AA}^4$	$b_5 = 0.00679690 \text{ \AA}$
	$c_5 = 0.04762012 \text{ \AA}$

The data description can also be characterized in terms of the dimensionless deviation for particular data, $DD_\alpha = \sqrt{\chi_\alpha^2 / N_\alpha}$, see Table 3. According to Press *et al.*,³⁴ this quantity should be close to unity for each subset of the data enumerated by α . We see that this condition is roughly fulfilled for the most of the data calculated with the irregular function, and the same figures are obtained for the rational and regular DMFs (not shown).

Table 3 Dimensionless deviations for particular data

data	irregular	rational
TDM	0.5	0.5
Intensity ratios ³³	2.1	2.3
Buldakov09 ¹⁶	0.5	0.7
ACPF, $r < 0.5$	0.6	1.2
ACPF, $r \geq 0.5$	0.6	0.5
ACPF, $r = 0.8-1.6 \text{ \AA}$	0.6	0.7
CCSD(T), $r < 0.5$	0.2	0.7
CCSD(T), $r \geq 0.5$	0.8	0.7
CCSD(T), $r = 0.8-1.6 \text{ \AA}$	0.8	0.9

Table 4 Average error (in %) of reproduction of the experimental TDMs by the irregular DMF fitted only to the *ab initio* data

band	ACPF+CCSD(T)	ACPF	CCSD(T)	exp
0-0	0.6	3.8	3.2	2.4
1-0	1.5	1.4	2.2	0.8
2-0	0.9	0.1	0.3	0.2
3-0	1.2	0.8	1.9	1.2
4-0	2.9	0.5	1.7	1.1
4-1	1.1	1.9	2.9	3.3
5-0	11.1	10.8	11.3	12.0
5-1	3.8	1.6	1.6	5.0
5-4	1.0	0.9	1.8	1.3
6-0	8.9	4.3	0.9	1.8
6-5	1.2	1.2	2.1	0.9
11-10	2.2	2.2	3.2	1.5

4.2 The NIDLs

The NIDL usually starts at $\nu > 2$ except for CO where the $\nu = 5$ anomaly in the dipole spectrum was predicted and observed many years ago, see **Medvedev21** (recently, it has been also predicted in the quadrupole spectrum³⁵). Therefore, we expect that the NIDL in CO will manifest at $\nu > 6$.

In Fig. 4, the R0-line intensities are shown for the $\nu=0$ bands. Perfectly straight NIDLs are seen at the top panel for the irregular and rational DMFs, as well as for the reference polynomial.

At the bottom panel, the R0-line intensities are shown for three regular DMFs, namely, regular 13 of Eq. (5), regular 14 of **Medvedev21**, and the latter with a simpler mapping function of $z_1(r)$ (simple regular). All NIDLs are wavy, and the waviness is different between them. The latter proves that *the waviness is a property of these particular artificial DMFs, and therefore all of them have nothing to do with the actual dipole-moment function*.

In discussing these results, we first note that only the irregular and rational DMFs generate the straight NIDL whereas all the regular DMFs fail to do that. Second, the reasons for such a behavior that we can advance are purely speculative since no deep theoretical study has been performed.

The success of the irregular and rational DMFs may be questioned because they have singularities that could contribute to the transition integral thereby destroying the NIDL. The answer can be that the singularities are located far from the region where the NIDL is formed, see Appendix A.

The failure of the regular functions to provide for the straight NIDL can be presumably explained by several reasons. The most important reason specific for all such functions is the fundamental impossibility to describe the irregular behavior with a regular function. This looks like trying to fit \sqrt{x} with a linear function, $ax + b$. Among other reasons, we suspect the mapping function of Eq. (6), which causes the fast DMF variation as r^{20} and the braces in the 7th degree in Eq. (5), which both may affect the transition integral.

Fig. 4 The $\nu=0$ ($\nu = 6-26$) R0-line strength in the NIDL coordinates calculated with Meshkov18 potential and various DMFs. *Upper panel*: black filled circles, irregular DMF; red empty circles, 8th-order polynomial; blue triangles, rational DMF. *Lower panel*: red triangles, regular 13 DMF from Meshkov22; green stars, previous regular 14 DMF from Medvedev21; blue rhombs, simple regular DMF (see text). The straight line, the same in both panels, is shown for comparison to demonstrate the straight NIDLs in the upper panel and the wavy NIDLs in the lower panel. Cross at $\nu = 6$ in both panels, the experimental point from Meshkov22. Color online.

4.3 Fitting to the *ab initio* data and predicting with such DMFs

Fitting the model DMF to the *ab initio* data has been previously used by Wong *et al.*²⁸ for nitric oxide as an alternative to spline interpolation employed in the DUO program.³⁶ The fitted DMF satisfactorily reproduced the observed $\Delta\nu = 0-7$ intensities, with the maximum difference of 50% for the 7-0 band (see Table 10

in Wong *et al.*), but showed large instability of predictions for unobserved higher overtones, $\Delta\nu > 7$, with respect to changes in the fitting details; moreover, huge instability was observed even for some observed transitions, e.g. by two orders of magnitude for the 5-0 band.

In the previous paper **Medvedev21**, we investigated the stability of the intensity predictions by particular DMFs with respect to variations in the input experimental data set to which these DMFs were fitted. Here, we will fit the DMFs to various subsets of the *ab initio* data in order to probe the stability of predictions with the DMFs that are not fitted to the experimental data at all.

First, an interesting question arises whether the experimental data can be reproduced by the DMFs fitted only to the *ab initio* data. The answer is “yes” provided that some precautions are made with respect to the unavoidable systematic errors in the data.

These errors are seen in Fig. 3 where differences between the DMFs fitted to the full database and the ACPF *data points* are shown. Obviously, the systematic error of about 0.01 D is present in the ACPF data. The CCSD(T) data contain the same systematic error of 0.01 D (not shown). The systematic errors must be taken into account when fitting only to the *ab initio* data because they will manifest in the calculated TDMs.

Next we consider the differences between the DMFs fitted to the full database and the ones fitted only to subsets of the *ab initio* data. The results for the irregular and regular 13 DMFs are shown in Fig. 5.

Let us first consider the fitting of the irregular DMF to the ACPF data at $r > 0.5$ Å and to the **Buldakov09** points. We obtain the wavy dashed line. This oscillation drastically affects the calculated intensities, thereby corrupting the NIDL, which tells us that the function is wrong. A conceivable reason is that the model is unable to follow the points containing the above systematic errors and simultaneously to obey the precise asymptotic limits.

The correct full line is obtained when the **Buldakov09** points are excluded from the fitting. The full line follows the respective differences from Fig. 3 very closely, which testifies that the irregular DMF fitted only to the ACPF points at $r > 0.5$ Å smoothly reproduces the ACPF points without any oscillations. For the regular 13 DMF, such oscillations are present both when **Buldakov09** points are included (dotted line) or not included (not shown).

In discussing these results, we remind that the purpose of this calculation is to verify the idea that the observed intensities can be restored from the *ab initio* DMF data. To perform this task, the model DMF is not required to satisfy the asymptotic limits, as in the case when one aims at predicting the intensities of higher transitions. Therefore, including the very short-range ACPF data in the fitting is unnecessary.

The numerical data supporting the above idea are presented in Table 4. The irregular DMF was fitted to either ACPF, CCSD(T), or both data sets, and the differences between the calculated and measured TDMs were averaged over the rotational lines within each band. The results are convincing: for the most of the bands, the differences are within 1-3%, close to the average experimen-

tal uncertainties of the data.[†] Similar results were obtained for the rational DMF except that the long-range coefficient was not fixed at the value of Eq. (2) whereas the **Buldakov09** points were included in the fitting (not shown).

Fig. 5 Difference between the DMFs fitted to the full database and the DMF fitted to the selected ACPF data only. Black full line, the irregular DMF, the ACPF data include only points at $r > 0.5$ Å, no **Buldakov09** points; black filled circles, the same as in Fig. 3, for comparison; red dashed line, the same as full line with **Buldakov09** points included; blue dotted line, regular 13, no **Buldakov09** points. Color online.

Next we consider the predictions of both the observed and unobserved lines made with the DMFs fitted only to the *ab initio* data. Figure 6 compares the intensities calculated with the DMFs fitted to the full database (points) with the ones calculated with the DMFs fitted only to the ACPF points (lines). We see that all the full-fit functions give similar intensities up to the 7-0 band except for the anomalies. However, when the experimental data are removed from the database, the reactions of these functions are cardinally different.

With the irregular and rational functions, nothing particular happens. For lower bands, the lines are indistinguishable from the corresponding points on this semi-logarithmic scale except that the intensities of the anomalies in the 4-0 and 7-0 bands are changed, as well as the anomaly position in the 10-0 band is shifted; these are well-known phenomena.³⁸ Notably, these “poorly defined” functions that know nothing about the experiment reproduce the observed intensities in the 4-0 band with a high precision (see *Inset*). The difference between the full-fit and ACPF-fit functions becomes appreciable only in the 10-0 band.

The behavior of the regular 13 function is quite different. Even in the lowest 2-0 band, the ACPF fit is already differs from the full fit, and the difference increases for higher overtones, making this ACPF-fit function senseless.

The rational DMF behaves much better. Therefore, at this level of comparison, the rational function looks not worse than the irregular DMF and can be used to verify the validity of the predictions by independent calculations.

[†]The larger differences for the 5-0 and 6-0 bands are presumably due to the fact that the 5-0 band is the anomaly.⁹

Fig. 6 Stability of the calculated intensities with respect to removal of the experimental data from the fit. Black circles, red pluses, and green crosses, the full-fit results for the irregular, regular 13, and rational DMFs, respectively; full, dash, and dash-dot lines, the ACPF-fit results for the irregular, regular 13, and rational DMFs, respectively; vertical strips in the 4-0 band, experimental data.³⁷ Inset in the Band 4-0 panel: The irregular DMF fitted only to the ACPF data perfectly reproduces the experimental data. Color online: black, irregular DMF; red, regular 13; green, rational; blue strips, experimental.

The conclusion from the above is obvious. The irregular and rational functions are highly stable with respect to the database, whereas the regular 13 one shows instability. In view of the results of the previous subsection, the full-fit irregular function has got the best extrapolation properties and therefore must be used for creating the line list whereas the full-fit regular 13 function can be used as a comparison DMF confirming the validity of predictions for the 7-0 band only. Moreover, *the comparison of the irregular DMF with the rational DMF demonstrates the validity of the calculations for the highest Δv transitions included in the present line lists*, see Sec. 7.

5 The line list

Using the **Meshkov18** potential and the present irregular DMF of Eq. (3), we calculated the line lists and the statistical sums for all nine CO isotopologues, see Supplementary material.[†] The line lists contain both Einstein A coefficients in s^{-1} and the line intensities in cm/molecule calculated at the standard temperature of 296 K assuming the 100% abundance. The range of quantum numbers is $v' \leq 41$, $\Delta v \leq 15$, and $J \leq 150$ (≤ 200 for the 0-0 and 1-0 bands). The column headings are explained in the supplementary **Readme.pdf** file.[†]

Figure 7 shows the relative deviations (in %) of the line intensities calculated with the irregular, rational, and regular DMFs from the observed ones, Eq. (8), for the 5-0 band of the principal isotopologue. This band is vibrational anomaly, its intensity is much less than the value predicted by the NIDL (see, e.g., **Medvedev21**). By this reason, it is very sensitive to the DMF form.³⁸ In particular, the difference between the irregular and regular DMFs manifest clearly. On the other hand, the difference between the irregular and rational DMFs does not exceed 1%, which is not seen in the figure.

The relative deviations for other bands of the main isotopologue and for minor isotopologues are given in supplementary figures S1 and S2.[†] These pictures look identical with the ones calculated with the regular DMF in **Meshkov22**. The following experimental data were used: bands 0-0,^{31,39} 1-0,⁴⁰⁻⁴² 2-0,^{41,43-45} 3-0,⁴⁶⁻⁵² 4-0,^{37,53-55} 5-0,⁵⁶ and 6-0.⁵⁷ Figures 7, S1, and S2 present the data for all lines observed. Quantitatively presented in Table 2 are the data for only those lines to which the functions were fitted. For all bands, the differences do not exceed the experimental uncertainties. The results for the irregular and rational DMFs are nearly identical for all bands (not shown).

Systematic errors in some experimental data are clearly seen in both figures. A detailed analysis of these data are given in **Meshkov22**.

6 The 7-0 band

The appearance of the 7-0 band has been already presented in Fig. 8 of **Medvedev21** and here in Fig. 6. As we noted, the validity of these predictions is supported by the fact that several functions with different analytical properties make similar predictions. Now we can compare the Einstein A coefficients obtained with different functions, namely, several variants of the irregular, regular, and rational DMFs, as well as polynomials. The relative differences of the predictions with respect to the basic irregular

Fig. 7 The relative deviations of the calculated and measured line intensities, Eq. (8), in the 5-0 band of the principal isotopologue, %. The calculations are performed with the irregular, regular, and rational DMFs. The difference between the irregular and regular DMFs manifest only in the 5-0 band (filled and empty circles, respectively). Data for other bands and minor isotopologues are shown in the Supplementary material,[†] see Figs. S1 and S2. In all bands including 5-0, the relative deviations for the irregular and rational DMFs are indistinguishable. Color online.

DMF of Eq. (3) fitted to the full database, $100(A - A_{\text{irreg}})/A_{\text{irreg}}$, are shown in Fig. 8.

It is seen that, far enough from the anomaly located at around $m = 100$, the differences are on the order of 20-30%. Notably, the predictions of the empirical 6th-order polynomial of **Li15** decline from the present irregular DMF by only 1-3% within the range of $m = -150$ to $+50$. In a vicinity of the anomaly, the predictions vary by a factor of 5 in accord with our previous finding of very high sensitivity of the anomalies to small variations of the PEF and DMF.³⁸ Thus, we expect that the error in the predicted 7-0 band intensities will not exceed 30% within the full P branch and the low- J (≤ 50) R branch.

Fig. 8 The relative differences (with respect to the final irregular DMF fitted to the full database) of the Einstein A coefficients predicted for the 7-0 band by several DMFs. Color online.

7 The 10-0 and 15-0 bands

Figure 9 compares the TDMs calculated with various functions in order to estimate the reliability of such data for the highest overtone bands included in the line lists. In our disposition, we have two functional forms of the irregular DMF, one in Eq. (3) and the other (with 16 parameters) in **Medvedev21**, the regular DMF in

Fig. 9 Validation of the line lists up to the 15-0 band calculated with the irregular DMF. The transition dipole moments calculated with the Meshkov18 potential and various dipole moment functions. *Filled symbols*: black circles, irregular 13, ACPF points at $r < 0.5 \text{ \AA}$ are not included in the fitting; blue triangles, irregular 13, all ACPF points are included in the fitting; cyan squares, irregular 16; orange rhombs, irregular pre1; purple stars, rational. *Empty symbols*: black squares, regular 13; red circles, pre2; green triangles, simple regular 16. *The left panels* compare predictions of various irregular DMFs and the rational DMF. Relatively small differences between the curves testify the validity of the rotational distributions calculated with the irregular function. *The right panels* compare predictions of various regular DMFs; their predictions are highly unreliable. Note the linear scale for the TDM. Color online.

Eq. (5), and the rational DMF in Eq. (7). Here, we refitted the irregular (16 parameters) and regular (14 parameters) functions in **Medvedev21** to the present database, they are denoted pre1 and pre2, respectively.

Four irregular DMFs, namely irregular 13 (twice), irregular 16, and pre1, and the rational DMF all show relative stability of the predicted transition moments. Thus, the TDM predicted by these functions varies within 10 and 40% in the 10-0 and 15-0 bands, respectively.

On the contrary, the regular DMFs diverge both between themselves and with the irregular DMFs. These results show that the irregular and rational DMFs are most suitable for extrapolation needed for the calculated line lists.

The data for the 15-0 band, the band with the highest $\Delta\nu$ in the line lists, permit us to assume that the calculated intensities, too small to be observed in the near future, have uncertainties of less than one order of magnitude. This follows from the comparison between the irregular and rational DMFs. For instance, the predicted $|TDMs|$ differ by a factor of 2 at $m = 0$.

8 Concluding remarks

The main result of the present work is creating the CO line lists and presenting empirical proofs of the reliability of the calculations up to the very high $\Delta\nu = 15$. A few final comments are also in order.

8.1 Such a complicated DMF

The final dipole moment function of carbon monoxide presented in Eq. (3) is quite cumbersome. Its complicated structure reflects the actual, very specific behavior of the intrinsic DMF with its two maxima, two minima, and three intersections with abscissa at $r > 0$, Fig. 2. The necessity to fulfil the known asymptotic limits of Eq. (1), especially to agree with the known long-range constant, Eq. (2), strongly restricted the choice of possible analytic forms capable to obey all these requirements.^{||} It is very probable that the same difficulties will be encountered with nitric oxide since its dipole moment behaves very similarly, see Fig. 6 in Buldakov and Cherepanov⁵⁸ and Fig. 2 in Wong *et al.*²⁸; in particular, the wavy NIDL is expected judging by Fig. 4 of Wong *et al.* For the DMFs with a simpler behavior, simple models like the regular functions or Padé approximants may work successfully.

It should be noted that the requirements to the dipole and potential are quite different. The potential is intended to provide for the high-precision energy levels. The semi-empirical **Meshkov18** potential⁸ indeed predicts the transition frequencies much better than the empirical potential due to Coxon and Hajigeorgiou,⁴ as demonstrated for the experimental 3-0 band^{46,59} in **Meshkov21**. However, there is a difficulty when it goes about the intensities. We will consider it below.

8.2 The difference in modelling PEF and DMF

The average energy E of an arbitrary state ψ is calculated as expectation value of the Hamiltonian, $E = \langle \psi \hat{H} \psi \rangle$. In particular, the energies of the stationary states obey the same equation. Since the integrand contains the wave function squared, no cancellation occurs, as in the transition dipole moment, so that the value of the integral is of the same order of magnitude as that of the integrand. For this reason, when constructing the model potential energy functions for calculating the energy levels, one has no need to impose special restrictions onto their analytical properties and to require extraordinary precision. In particular, the model PEF may have nonphysical singularities in the complex plane. Moreover, the PEF may exhibit non-physical behavior even in a part of the real axis, which is the case for the **Coxon04** potential.

The **Meshkov18** potential indeed has nonphysical singularities, which are of no importance for energy levels but may be a reason for errors in the intensity calculations.

As we have noted already, the transition-dipole-moment integral for high overtones is many orders of magnitude smaller than the value of the integrand at the real axis. By this reason, small relative errors in the DMF and PEF can lead to huge relative errors in the TDM. Thus, the accuracy of the DMF and PEF on the real axis tells nothing about the precision of the intensity calculations. As follows from the theory described in Appendix A, the integration path can be shifted into the complex plane in such a way that the integrand becomes on the order of the whole integral. In this case, the error in the integral is of the same order as that in the integrand. Note that various model functions that are almost

indistinguishable at the real axis can differ significantly in the complex plane. This explains why the respective values of TDMs can differ by many orders of magnitude.[§] Thus, in order to obtain reliable values of intensities of high overtones, it is necessary that the analytical continuation of the model functions into the essential region of the complex plane reproduced the behavior of the physical functions in this region. The presence of non-physical singularities in the model functions can be an obstacle to this.

Therefore, in future, if higher precision for the high- Δv transitions is required, the potential should be modified in such a way that to contain only the simple pole at $r = 0$ due to the nuclear Coulomb repulsion and the branch points at the same positions as in the dipole function of Eq. (3), with the same square roots moved to the numerator and with modified factors responsible for the behavior in both asymptotic limits. The parameters of the model PEF and DMF must be fitted simultaneously to the data on the line positions and intensities.

8.3 Spin-orbit coupling

The PEF and DMF used in the present work have been obtained with no account of the spin-orbit coupling. In particular, the fine structure of the atomic levels have been ignored when considering the long-range asymptotics. However, the spin-orbit splitting in carbon and oxygen is pretty large. The minimal fine-structure intervals in carbon and oxygen are 16.4 and 158.26 cm^{-1} , respectively.⁶⁰ In fact, the spin-orbit energy in these atoms exceeds their electrostatic interaction at the distances larger than 5 Å. The ground state of CO at large r correlates with an O state fifth-fold degenerate in the projection of the total angular momentum, and all matrix elements of the operator of quadrupole-quadrupole interaction between the components of this state vanish, i.e. the electrostatic interaction can contribute only in the second order of the perturbation theory.

Thus, in order to establish the correct behavior of the PEF and DMF at $r > 5$ Å, both in the *ab initio* calculations and in frames of the perturbation theory, the spin-orbit coupling in the atoms has to be taken into account. The *ab initio* data used in our work and the analysis of the long-range behavior in frames of the perturbation theory have only model character. Nevertheless, this is not an obstacle for using them to construct the semi-empirical potential and dipole-moment functions. As follows from the theory presented in Appendix A, the main exponential dependence of the overtone intensities is determined by factor T_0 depending only on the repulsive branch of the potential in the range from zero up to the left turning point in the lower state. The pre-factor is slow function of the overtone number. It is given by the integral along a complex path C , and the main contribution comes from a part of C close to the region of the classical motion. The requirement for the asymptotic parameter d_4 to be restricted by Eq. (2) is not critically important for the semi-empirical DMF, therefore d_4 can be used, if necessary, as adjustable parameter. Such a possibility

[§]The inverse statement is also valid: If two functions coincide along complex path C so that the predicted TDMs are nearly the same, the functions can essentially differ at the real axis.

^{||} See, however, Sec. 8.3.

was indeed realized in the present work in order to reach good description of all available information in the process of fitting the semi-empirical rational function.

Supplementary material[†]

File **LineList_Irregular-13_5007.zip**. Line lists of all nine CO isotopologues calculated with the irregular DMF having 13 adjustable parameters.

File **Readme.pdf** explains the meaning of the column headings in the line lists.

File **DMF_Irreg_13.f**. FORTRAN code for the irregular DMF with 13 adjustable parameters.

File **DMF_Rational.f**. FORTRAN code for the rational DMF with 14 adjustable parameters. The code uses coefficients of the 10th-order polynomial rather than its poles shown in Table 1.

File **Q.zip**. Statistical sums for all isotopologues calculated with the **Meshkov18** potential at $T = 1-9000$ K. The same as in **Meshkov22**.

File **d4_data_analysis.pdf**. Precise determination of the long-range coefficient.

File **Figs_S1_and_S2.pdf**. Comparison of the calculated and measured intensities. The same as in **Meshkov22** except for the 5-0 band.

A Where the NIDL comes from?

An unusual property of the high-overtone TDM integral, Eq. (9) below, is its very low value as compared to the integrand, which is in sharp contrast to the low-overtone transitions.

Consider, for instance, the fundamental band of CO. The experimental transition dipole moment (TDM) varies between 0.104 and 0.106 D over the entire band, $J \leq 30$, as follows from the Devi *et al.*⁴⁰ intensity data recalculated to TDM in Meshkov *et al.*¹ As can be seen from Fig. 2, the value of the DMF in the spectroscopic region (1-1.3 Å) over which the TDM integral is calculated is within 0.1-0.5 D, i.e. of the same order of magnitude as the TDM itself. Therefore, the uncertainty of the TDM is similar to that of the DMF. Consider next the 4-0 band. The absolute value of the TDM varies in the limits of $(1-3)10^{-5}$ D for $J \leq 34$ as follows from the Bordet *et al.*³⁷ intensity data recalculated to TDM in Meshkov *et al.*¹ In such a case, where the integral is five orders of magnitude smaller than the integrand, small relative errors in the DMF can result in huge relative errors in the TDM, therefore the precision of the DMF values tells nothing about the precision of the intensity calculations. Our task is to avoid the errors introduced by an incorrect choice of the model DMF.

The matrix element of the dipole moment is calculated as the integral along the real axis,

$$\text{TDM} = \int_0^{\infty} \psi_{v'} d(r) \psi_v dr, \quad (9)$$

where $\psi_{v'}$ and ψ_v are the wave functions of the lower and upper states, respectively.** The wave functions decrease exponentially at small and large r along the real axis outside the turning points in the respective states and oscillate in-between. The oscillation results in unusually low TDM values. As noted above, the observed 4-0 TDM value is 5 orders of magnitude lower than the DMF itself in the spectroscopic region. Where, then, this small value comes from?

In order to answer this question, we move the integration path into the complex plane. This transformation does not affect the TDM value unless there are singularities of the integrand, $d(r)$ and ψ 's, on the way between the real axis and the new path C . We assume that both the DMF and PEF obey this rule.

When shifted into the complex plane, both wave functions increase exponentially in the lower and upper half-planes. Following Landau and Lifshitz,²⁷ we represent the wave function of the excited state, $\psi_{v'}$, as a sum of two linearly independent solutions of the Schrödinger equation, $\psi_{v'}^+$ and $\psi_{v'}^-$, where $\psi_{v'}^+$ decreases in the upper half-plane and $\psi_{v'}^-$ decreases in the lower half-plane. On the real axis, these functions are complex conjugate to each other, and the matrix element of the dipole moment can be written as

$$\text{TDM} = 2\text{Re} \int_0^{\infty} \psi_{v'} d(r) \psi_v^+ dr \equiv 2\text{Re} \int_C \psi_{v'} d(r) \psi_v^+ dr, \quad (10)$$

** We omit the rotational quantum numbers.

where C is a new integration path in the complex plane. Since ψ_v^+ decreases in the upper half-plane faster than $\psi_{v'}$ increases,^{19,27} the integrand decreases exponentially in the upper half-plane.

There is an essential difference in the behavior of the integrands in Eqs. (9) and (10). In Eq. (9), the integrand decays to the left of the left turning point in the upper state, r_v^- , so rapidly that the integration can be truncated immediately after r_v^- where both wave functions decrease exponentially. In contrast, in the integrand of Eq. (10), function ψ_v^+ increases, thereby compensating in part the decrease of $\psi_{v'}$ (the later decreases faster than the former increases so that the integral converges). For this reason, the integration along C must be performed from the very $r = 0$, where the answer to the title question will be found, as we will see below. Another feature to note is that the integration path in Eq. (9) cannot be shifted from the real axis because both functions increase in the upper and lower half-planes, hence the integrand cannot be diminished as needed. On the contrary, in Eq. (10), function ψ_v^+ , first, decreases in the upper half-plane, and second, it decreases faster than $\psi_{v'}$ increases so that the integrand can be diminished in absolute value.

If C is moved far away from the turning points in both states, the wave functions can be written in the quasi-classical approximation.²⁷ Along path C , functions ψ_v and ψ_v^+ have the form

$$\psi_v = \frac{A_v}{\sqrt{q_v}} \frac{e^{-iS_v/\hbar + i\pi/4}}{\sqrt{p_v}}, \quad (11)$$

$$\psi_v^+ = A_v \sqrt{q_v} \frac{e^{iS_v/\hbar - i\pi/4}}{\sqrt{p_v}}, \quad (12)$$

where

$$p_v = \sqrt{2\mu [E_v - U(r)]} \quad (13)$$

is classical momentum and

$$S_v = \int_{r_v^-}^r p_v dr \quad (14)$$

is classical action. The quasi-classical normalization constant is

$$A_v = \frac{(-1)^v}{\sqrt{Q_v}}, \quad (15)$$

where

$$Q_v = 2 \int_{r_v^-}^{r_v^+} \frac{dr}{p_v}, \quad (16)$$

r_v^\mp are the left and right turning points, and multiplier $(-1)^v$ is introduced according to the conventional definition of the sign of the wave functions. Parameter q_v in Eqs. (11) and (12) is harmonic correction to the quasi-classical normalization constant,

$$q_v = \frac{v! e^{v+1/2}}{\sqrt{2\pi} (v+1/2)^{v+1/2}}. \quad (17)$$

It equals approximately to 0.93 for $v = 0$, 0.97 for $v = 1$, and tends to unity at $v > 1$.

The exponential behavior of the integrand in Eq. (10) is deter-

mined by factor

$$T(r) = \exp\left(i\hbar^{-1}\Delta S(r)\right), \quad (18)$$

where

$$\Delta S(r) \equiv S_{v'} - S_v = \int_{r_v^-}^r p_{v'} dr - \int_{r_v^-}^r p_v dr \quad (19)$$

is the difference between the classical actions S_v in the two states under consideration. The quasi-classical approximation is valid when $|S_v|/\hbar \gg 1$. In our problem, this quantity is about 1500 in a vicinity of $r = 0$ for both states. Calculations show that the TDMs for the $v=0$ bands calculated with the quasi-classical functions differ from the exact ones by 0.003% for $v = 0$ and on the order of 0.1% for $v > 20$ (not shown).

Figure 10 illustrates the behavior of

$$\Delta(r) \equiv \text{Re } i\hbar^{-1}\Delta S(r) \quad (20)$$

in the complex plane for the 10-0 overtone transition. It is seen that $|T(r)| \equiv \exp[\Delta(r)]$ reaches maximum in the region of classical motion around equilibrium at $r_e \approx 1 \text{ \AA}$ and then decreases exponentially when displaced from this region both along the real axis and into the upper half-plane. White lines show the levels of $\Delta(r) = \text{const}$.

Fig. 10 The real function $\Delta(r)$ of Eq. (20) calculated for the 10-0 transition.

Now let us shift the integration path from the real axis to path C in order to circumvent the mountain. The purpose is to diminish $|T(r)|$ along C so that it would become on the order of the final TDM value. Indeed, the figure shows that C can be chosen such that $|T(r)|$ first slightly increases from its initial value of $T_0 \equiv T(0)$ but then decreases very rapidly. Let us factorize the TDM of Eq. (10) as

$$\text{TDM} = B_0 T_0. \quad (21)$$

As can be seen in Fig. 10, $\Delta(r)$ changes insignificantly, by about unity, from its initial value of -17 along the part of C that contributes to the full integral, say up to $\text{Re } r \approx 1.2 \text{ \AA}$ (see Fig. 12, where the integrand value is shown along the path). When moving along C continues, the absolute value of $\Delta(r)$ rapidly increases so that the rest of the path does not contribute to B_0 . This prop-

erty does not depend on the overtone number, therefore B_0 is a slow function of $\Delta\nu$.

On the contrary, factor T_0 depending only on the potential is responsible for the exponential decrease in the matrix element as the overtone number increases, i.e. for the NIDL since $|\Delta(0)|$ increases by approximately 1.7 between the successive overtones.^{††} Thus, the exponential behavior of the matrix elements turns out to be a direct consequence of the exponential behavior of the wave functions, and the steepness of this behavior, i.e. the NIDL slope, depends only on the potential energy. The main contribution to the B_0 integral is provided by the initial part of path C which starts at $r = 0$, circumvents the peak, and then the integrand proportional to $T(r)$ sharply falls down as shown in Fig. 10. *This is the answer to the title question.*

Fig. 11 Einstein A coefficient calculated either with the original DMF (circles) or with the TDM replaced by factor T_0 (crosses). Points are for the ν -0R0, $\nu = 6$ -26 lines normalized to the 6-0 transitions.

The numerical illustration is presented in Fig. 11 where plotted are the A coefficients for the R0 lines in the ν -0 bands calculated either with the original DMF or with T_0 substituted for the TDM. It is seen that both sets of data follow nearly one and the same NIDL over the entire range of transitions. The remaining B_0 integral depending on both the PEF and DMF is a slow function of ν : the intensities change by 12 orders of magnitude whereas their ratio due to B_0 changes only by about 12 times.

Figure 12 depicts the real part of the integrand in Eq. (10) along path C (the imaginary part is of the same order of magnitude, not shown). Two important features are to be noted. First, the quasi-classical approximation works perfectly for path C going far enough from all turning points. Second, the absolute value of the integrand is $\sim 10^{-8} \text{ D}\text{\AA}^{-1}$, i.e. much closer to the TDM value^{||} ($\sim 10^{-9} \text{ D}$) than the integrand at the real axis.^{‡‡} Remind that the integration along the real axis leads to cancellation of the

Fig. 12 The real part of the integrand of the transition integral for the 10-0 band along path C . The value of the integrand along path C is 8 orders of magnitude smaller than along the real axis.

large-amplitude vibrations of the wave functions by many orders of magnitude. This reasoning confirms that the small TDM value comes from the value of the integrand at path C .

Fig. 13 The ν -0R0 line TDMs squared for $\nu = 1$ -40 calculated with the Meshkov18 potential and the present irregular DMF either exactly (black filled circles) or quasi-classically (red empty circles). Since the exact calculation along the real axis leads to cancellation of the integrand by many orders of magnitude, quadruple precision is required at $\nu > 26$. For the quasi-classical calculation, double precision is sufficient for all ν 's.

Figure 13 demonstrates the specificity of the quasi-classical calculation along path C . First, precision is very high, small differences on the order of 0.1% with the exact values are not seen at this semi-logarithmic scale up to $\nu = 26$. Second, at $\nu = 26$, the cancellation of the integrand along the real axis decreases the resulting TDM by 13 orders of magnitude, therefore higher ν 's require quadruple precision when the calculation is performed by Eq. (9). In contrast, the oscillation along C cancels only one order of magnitude, so that double precision is sufficient to calculate the TDMs up to $\nu = 40$; moreover, even simple precision would be sufficient.

What should we learn from the above calculations? We assumed that neither the potential nor the dipole moment have got singularities in the upper half-plane that would prevent us from

^{††} $|\Delta(0)|$ increases from 0 at $\nu = 0$ to 17 at $\nu = 10$.

^{||} In order to compare with the TDM, the integrand must be multiplied by the width of the integration region, which is on the order of 1 \AA .

^{‡‡} In principle, the integrand value might be diminished even more, down to the TDM value, provided that C could be moved farther; however, the latter cannot be performed with Meshkov18 potential having poles in the complex plane.

displacing the integration path to the C path. Only in such a case the straight NIDL line will manifest. Since there are no physical reasons for such singularities, we have to adopt that any distortion of the NIDL is caused by non-physical analytical properties of the model molecular functions.

If the model DMF rapidly increases in the upper half-plane, the value of the integrand along path C increases as well, leading to the appearance of saddle points at the path. As a result, the values of the calculated intensities greatly increase. The models that strongly oscillate along C , on the contrary, lead to a strong decrease in B_0 . In any case, the NIDL shape is distorted, it becomes wavy.

A final remark is in order with respect to the wide plateau (where $\Delta(r) \approx -17$) extending from $\text{Re } r = 0$ until $\approx 0.7 \text{ \AA}$ seen in Fig. 10. As follows from the definition in Eq. (20), the derivative of $\Delta(r)$ is proportional to the difference of momenta. Multiplying and dividing by their sum, we obtain

$$\Delta'(r) \propto \frac{E_{\nu'} - E_{\nu''}}{p_{\nu'} + p_{\nu''}}. \quad (22)$$

When the potential becomes much greater than the energy difference, the first and all higher derivatives vanish. This happens at $r_* \in 0.6\text{-}0.8 \text{ \AA}$ where the difference $\Delta(0) - \Delta(r_*)$ becomes on the order of unity. If we redefine T_0 by replacing the $r = 0$ end point with r_* , the NIDL will be preserved and B_0 will remain a slow function of ν . Yet, the "range of influence" of the PEF and DMF singularities is moved away from the coordinate origin. This might explain why the branch point of the irregular DMF near 0.4 \AA does not affect the NIDL. We also note that, by the same reason, the Coxon and Hajigeorgiou empirical potential⁴ does not break the NIDL despite it turns over at $r \approx 0.6 \text{ \AA}$.

Author Contributions

E.S. Medvedev: Conceptualization, Project administration, Writing – original draft, review & editing. *V.G. Ushakov*: Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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